

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

Final Exploitation and replication plan

D6.3

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The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
APRE	Agency for the Promotion of European Research
BG	Background
CA	Consortium Agreement
DC	Dissemination & Communication
DFBG	District of Fisheries and Blue Growth, Sicily
DoA	Description of Action
EMÜ	Estonian University of Life Sciences
ER	Exploitable Results
EU	European Union
FBCD	Food & BioCluster Denmark
FG	Foreground
LOBA	LOBA
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IP	Intellectual Property
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
NGOs	Non-governmental Organisations
NIBIO	The Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research
NDA	Non-disclosure Agreement
R&D	Research and Development
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
UIA	University of Agder
UNIPA	University of Palermo
WP	Work Package

Index of Contents

1	Executive Summary	9
2	Introduction	10
2.1	The Exploitation Guidelines	11
2.2	IPR Approach	12
3	Exploitation Methodology	14
3.1	Adopted definitions	14
3.1.1	Exploitation	14
3.1.2	Valorisation	15
4	Analysis and Exploitation Strategy of BlueRev KERs	16
4.1	KER1: Novel business and governance models, models for social innovations (D3.3, D4.1, D4.2, D4.3)	17
4.1.1	Challenge	17
4.1.2	Asset Description	17
4.1.3	Stakeholders Targeted and Expected Benefits	19
4.1.4	Unique Selling Point	20
4.1.5	Report of Exploitation activities already carried out	21
4.1.6	Exploitation And Sustainability Recommendations	21
4.2	KER2: Guidelines reporting the best practices demonstrated in pilot regions D4.4 23	
4.2.1	Challenge	23
4.2.2	Asset Description	23
4.2.3	Stakeholders Targeted and Expected Benefits	23
4.2.4	Unique Selling Point	24
4.2.5	Report of Exploitation activities already carried out	25
4.2.6	Exploitation And Sustainability Recommendations	25
4.3	KER3: Training programme and materials D5.1, D5.2	26
4.3.1	Challenge	26
4.3.2	Asset Description	27
4.3.3	Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits	27
4.3.4	Unique Selling Point	28
4.3.5	Report of Exploitation activities already carried out	28

4.3.6	Exploitation And Sustainability Recommendations	28
4.4	KER4: Guidelines supporting the development of communication of innovation	
D5.4	30	
4.4.1	Challenge	30
4.4.2	Asset Description.....	30
4.4.3	Stakeholders Targeted and Expected Benefits	31
4.4.4	Unique Selling Point	31
4.4.5	Report of Exploitation activities already carried out.....	32
4.4.6	Exploitation and Sustainability Recommendations.....	32
4.5	KER5: Support Tool.....	33
4.5.1	Challenge	33
4.5.2	Asset Description.....	33
4.5.3	Stakeholders Targeted and Expected Benefits	34
4.5.4	Unique Selling Point	34
4.5.5	Exploitation and Sustainability Recommendations.....	35
4.6	Post-project exploitation at a glance	36
5	Report On Exploitation Activities Already Carried Out.....	37
5.1	Validation and transfer of new solutions: Italian HUB.....	39
5.1.1	Introduction.....	39
5.1.2	Case study context.....	40
5.1.3	Activities	41
5.1.4	Outcomes.....	43
5.1.5	Findings and recommendations.....	43
5.2	Validation and transfer of new solutions: Estonian HUB	44
5.2.1	Introduction.....	44
5.2.2	Case study context.....	45
5.2.3	Activities	46
5.2.4	Outcomes.....	47
5.2.5	Findings and recommendations.....	47
5.3	Validation and transfer of new solutions: Danish HUB	48
5.3.1	Introduction.....	48
5.3.2	Case study context.....	48
5.3.3	Activities	49

5.3.4	Outcomes	50
5.3.5	Findings and recommendations	50
5.4	Validation and transfer of new solutions: Greenlandic HUB	51
5.4.1	Introduction.....	51
5.4.2	Case study context.....	51
5.4.3	Activities	51
5.4.4	Outcomes.....	56
5.4.5	Findings and recommendations.....	57
5.5	Final conference.....	57
5.5.1	Findings and recommendations.....	58
6	Conclusions	62

Index of Tables

Index of tables

Table 1: List of BlueRev KERs, in relation to specific deliverables, Work Packages, and the responsible partner for delivery	16
Table 2: Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits for KER 1	20
Table 3: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 1	23
Table 4: Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits for KER 2	24
Table 5: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 2	26
Table 6: Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits for KER 3	28
Table 7: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 3	30
Table 8: Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits for KER 4	31
Table 9: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 4	33
Table 10: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 5	35
Table 11: Zenodo statistics	39

Index of Figures

Figure 1: Support tool footer.	34
Figure 2: Presentation on Business models	52
Figure 3: Presentation on governance models	52
Figure 4: Presentation on social innovation.....	54
Figure 5: Pictures from the workshop.....	55

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable starts from the plan for exploitation and replication presented in D6.2 for the BlueRev project, and describes the activities performed to ensure the timely promotion of the project's outcomes and engagement of parties outside the Consortium, interested in using or adopting them. This document highlights the strategy implemented for the exploitation and gives suggestions for further expansions.

The consortium identified 4 project Key Exploitable Results (KERs) since the proposal phase (KER 1-4 listed below) and during the activities described in D6.2, the additional KER 5 was added. These KERs are being already exploited or will be exploited after the end of BlueRev, to ensure a viable exit strategy for achieving long lasting impacts:

1. KER1: Novel business and governance models, models for social innovations (D3.3, D4.1, D4.2, D4.3)
2. KER2: Training programme and materials (D5.1, D5.2)
3. KER3: Guidelines reporting the best practices demonstrated in pilot regions (D4.4)
4. KER4: Guidelines supporting the development of communication of innovation. (D5.4)
5. KER5: Online platform (Support Tool)

For the purpose of this document, these KERs have been analysed according to the following parameters:

1. Challenges
2. Asset description
3. Stakeholders targeted and expected benefits
4. Unique selling point
5. Exploitation and sustainability recommendations

2 Introduction

The BlueRev project is a Horizon Europe-funded initiative that seeks to develop and implement socially innovative models within the blue bioeconomy, focusing on sustainable practices in regions heavily dependent on marine resources. The project addresses the pressing need for environmental stewardship and social inclusivity by creating frameworks that enable local stakeholders to adopt and sustain environmentally responsible practices. By employing social innovation principles, BlueRev aims to increase local ownership of sustainability initiatives, enhance economic resilience, and strengthen regional collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including local governments, businesses, and community organizations.

BlueRev is implemented by a consortium of institutions from multiple countries, including research organizations, government bodies and NGOs. Through a multidisciplinary approach combining social innovation theories, empirical research, and stakeholder engagement, the project develops and tests models that can be scaled and adapted across various contexts within the European Union's blue bioeconomy.

Core goals of the BlueRev project include:

- Developing and demonstrate social innovation, governance and business models that address sustainable practices in the blue bioeconomy.
- Engaging a diverse range of stakeholders to ensure inclusivity and responsiveness to local needs.
- Establishing a framework for knowledge-sharing and policy development that supports sustainability in the marine sectors.

The present deliverable, part of WP6 “Dissemination: Communication, dissemination and exploitation”, aims to provide the final BlueRev exploitation strategy, with the ambition to guide post-project exploitation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs, namely assets that could be utilised beyond the project duration (the terms “asset” and KER are used interchangeably in this report). This document outlines the consortium plan to exploit and make project findings and results sustainable and attractive for the relevant market, to achieve a long-lasting impact after the project lifecycle, and a continuous cooperation among the identified and targeted stakeholders.

This document starts from the plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities outlined in D6.1¹ and D6.2², where the main assets for the KER were identified and analysed.

It is structured into six main chapters, expanding on the scheme illustrated above:

- **Chapter 1:** Executive Summary
- **Chapter 2:** Introduction

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682336>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10604265>

- **Chapter 3:** Exploitation Methodology. This chapter presents the strategy for sustaining BlueRev results through the analysis of Key Exploitable Results and defines exploitation and valorisation to guide long-term use and impact beyond the project.
- **Chapter 4:** Analysis and Exploitation Strategy of BlueRev KERs. This chapter analyses Key Exploitable Results using a common framework to highlight their purpose, impact, and exploitation potential across the blue bioeconomy.
- **Chapter 5:** Report on Exploitation Activities Already Carried Out: Validation and transfer of new solutions for the development of blue growth at the local level. This chapter details how knowledge resources from Chapter 4 supported stakeholder workshops across four regions, how materials developed within the project were integrated into training efforts, enriched by visual tools, and widely dissemination to enhance outreach and project impact.
- **Chapter 6:** Conclusions

2.1 The Exploitation Guidelines

The BlueRev Exploitation guidelines described in D6.1 and D6.2 set the strategy for mainstreaming and upscaling project results in order to guarantee the Valorisation, Multiplication and Sustainability of the project.

The exploitation strategy is in line with the needs of the fulfilment of the contractual expectations that respond to:

- European Commission's (EC) requirement to communicate the consortium's strategy and report on planned exploitation activities.
- Consortium partners need to inform participants about required activities and responsibilities concerning the exploitation of the results after the project ends.

Within the BlueRev project, exploitation activities focused on:

- the involvement of decision-makers at the political level to ensure mainstreaming of the project results.
- disseminating project results among end-users and promoting their use, satisfying the multiplication perspective.

For the above to succeed, the project coordinator, all the partners and key actors need to embrace exploitation as an ongoing process that expands beyond the project's life, ensuring the long-term sustainability of its results: "Exploitation focuses on the actual use of the results, translating research concepts into concrete solutions that have a positive impact on the public's quality of life"³.

³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/dissemination-and-exploitation-research-results_en

The initial exploitation plan (D6.2) set the activities related to the exploitation of the results by end users and/or potential users, and for the benefit of target groups clearly identified from the project design stage. To achieve these goals during the implementation, it elaborated the following issues:

- Define clearly and keep on identifying the target groups/end users/public and political stakeholders of the project's results;
- Ensure that these identified target groups/end users/public and political stakeholders will be involved during the lifetime of the project;
- Clarify how, during, and after the end of the project, the results will be exploited and sustained;
- Guarantee that the project results are available and visible after project conclusion;
- Ensure that the network created by the project is enriched sustainably;
- Ensure that the transfer of knowledge and good practices is set up.

Moreover, the initial exploitation plan provided an overview of the BlueRev activities and results. It was intended to serve as a guide for all partners, outlining their specific activities and responsibilities beyond the official end date of the project. The specific objectives of the exploitation activities are:

- To promote and raise awareness about the project contents, developments, and results;
- To successfully transfer the results to appropriate decision-makers to achieve their sustainable promotion and support;
- To convince end-users to adopt and/or apply the results, also after the project and support by its partnership has ended.

2.2 IPR Approach

As already described in the initial exploitation plan (D6.2), BlueRev IP handling procedures were applied among the partners to organise the results/assets management of the project. The background, foreground, assets' ownership, access rights, and protection, as well as the exploitation and commercialisation of the project's results, were identified in D6.2 using the IPR matrix methodology.

At the following stage, partners focused on two different points:

- Providing access rights to their knowledge for other partners to carry out their work on the project.
- Establishing early asset identification procedures to protect, disseminate, and exploit the project's assets.

The identified exploitable results and assets of BlueRev will be effectively exploited without any commercial use during the BlueRev project. In particular, the BlueRev consortium found exploitation opportunities for the project's results in:

- i) Further research activities, including new European Projects;
- ii) Further training sessions.

The KERs use is and will remain open without restrictions after the end of the project. Moreover, partners are committed to remaining the key contact points and providing support to future stakeholders interested in further using the project's results.

3 Exploitation Methodology

To lay the foundation for BlueRev exploitation strategy, as well as to ensure sustainability to project results after the end of the project, the consortium reaffirmed the context analysis defined in the early stage, considering the active policies in the project area of activity, the main target domains to be addressed, the target stakeholders interested in exploiting BlueRev results and the expected benefits, as well as the Stakeholder Database, developed under WP2.

Based upon the context analysis, the KERs already presented in the first version of the exploitation plan (D6.2) have been confirmed.

Each KER is analysed according to 6 parameters, as follows:

1. **Challenges:** the first parameter explains why the asset is needed, to understand the need/challenge that it addresses.
2. **Asset description:** the second parameter is the overview of the asset.
3. **Stakeholders targeted and expected benefits:** the third parameter identifies the stakeholders addressed and how they can benefit from it.
4. **Unique selling point:** the fourth parameter presents the most relevant value of the asset, identifying a value marketing proposition to ensure its exploitation potential.
5. **Report of Exploitation activities already carried out:** an overview of exploitation activities already implemented during the project life.
6. **Exploitation and sustainability recommendations:** the recommendations for the asset exploitation after the project, including the sustainability conditions to make it available, usable and reusable also by external stakeholders.

3.1 Adopted definitions

3.1.1 Exploitation

Exploitation is associated with the use of the project's results at different levels, during and after the implementation of the project. It is related to the necessary action that will bring visibility to the project in order to involve the target groups, end-users, stakeholders, and transfer the results/products into their professional scope. Exploitation is mostly related to the idea of convincing the key actors to use the main products of a project. Exploitation is strongly associated with the sustainability of the project after its conclusion since exploitation activities should ensure that the results of the project are used by its target groups and possibly are transferred to other contexts (e.g. other countries, other areas, other sectors).

The exploitation is split into two components: mainstreaming and multiplication. Mainstreaming means addressing the decision-makers in order to encourage them to take into account the results of the project, while multiplication is more focused on persuading individual end-users to adopt those products. This usage can be within the partnership and outside, at the local, regional, national, or European level. As in the case of dissemination, the exploitation process should be planned and organised at the

beginning of the project by a methodological document (e.g. Exploitation Strategy) that orients the whole consortium.

3.1.2 Valorisation

Valorisation is a term that includes dissemination and exploitation, and it aims to make the project results more valuable to everybody, meaning to make “others” use the product. Valorisation is the sum of both dissemination and exploitation activities. The overall objective of valorisation activities is to promote the project and its results and foster their use by different individuals and organisations, with the aim of constantly spreading and improving the usage and the content of the results. Valorisation involves not only the testing and dissemination of the results of the most innovative projects but also the exploitation of these results and their development in new contexts and environments. It includes the sustainable application of these results over time in formal and informal systems, in the practices of organisations, as well as in the personal learning goals of every individual. Valorisation means planning in such a way that the resources allocated to a project generate results that can be used and exploited on a large scale, with the view of benefiting as many individuals and organisations as possible. Valorisation must be based on a meticulous ex-ante analysis of needs to be fulfilled by a project, as well as on a clear identification of the results expected, and this from the beginning. Effective valorisation requires the active involvement, at the project design stage, of the potential users and target groups who are to benefit from the project and who are ultimately expected to exploit the results.

4 Analysis and Exploitation Strategy of BlueRev KERs

This section presents an in-depth analysis of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) generated within the BlueRev project. Each KER is linked to specific deliverables and Work Packages (WP) (see Table 1) and reflects the project's ambition to catalyse sustainable transformation in the blue bioeconomy across Europe. The analysis applies a uniform framework to ensure comparability, outlining the core challenge addressed, the nature of the asset, targeted stakeholders, unique strengths, exploitation strategies, and activities undertaken so far.

KER N°	Name of KER	Del. N	DOI	WP	Resp. Partner	Involved partners
1.1	KPIs and tools for selecting good practice methods	D3.3	10.5281/zenodo.15877789	WP3	NIBIO	RISE, UIA
1.2	Novel social innovation models	D4.1	10.5281/zenodo.14063593	WP4	NIBIO	
1.3	Novel business models	D4.2	10.5281/zenodo.14195789	WP4	UIA	NIBIO; RISE; EMU
1.4	Novel governance models	D4.3	10.5281/zenodo.14169028	WP4	RiSe	
2.0	Training programme and materials	D5.1	10.5281/zenodo.14353832	WP5	FBCD	EMU; UNIPA; APRE
		D5.3	10.5281/zenodo.15878391	WP5	UNIPA	EMU; APRE
3.0	Guidelines reporting the best practices demonstrated in pilot regions	D4.4	10.5281/zenodo.14731330	WP4	UIA	NIBIO; APRE EMU; RISE
4.0	Guidelines supporting the development of communication of innovation.	D5.4	10.5281/zenodo.15094850	WP5	APRE	EMU, FBCD, UNIPA (for local best practices)
5.0	Support Tool	/	BlueRev Support Tool	WP2	LOBA	

Table 1: List of BlueRev KERs, in relation to specific deliverables, Work Packages, and the responsible partner for delivery

4.1 KER1: Novel business and governance models, models for social innovations (D3.3, D4.1, D4.2, D4.3)

This Key Exploitable Result (KER1) combines four core deliverables—**D3.3 (KPIs and tools for selecting good practice methods)**, **D4.1 (Novel social innovation models)**, **D4.2 (Novel business models)**, and **D4.3 (Novel governance models)**—into an integrated set of conceptual and operational assets that support systemic innovation in the blue bioeconomy.

4.1.1 Challenge

Stakeholders across Europe's blue bioeconomy, particularly in coastal and rural regions, face complex, interrelated challenges that go far beyond technical or environmental concerns. The diversity of actors, regional conditions, and resource types makes it difficult to apply a one-size-fits-all approach. Furthermore, the absence of integrated tools for assessing good practices across environmental, social, economic, and governance dimensions limits the ability of actors to make evidence-based decisions aligned with the goals of circular and bio-based transitions.

In many areas, **social innovation** is hindered by fragmented networks, limited trust among actors, and a lack of inclusive, participatory processes that can foster behavioral change or community-led initiatives. Similarly, **governance systems** often suffer from misalignment between local, regional, and EU-level policies, resulting in regulatory uncertainty, siloed decision-making, and a limited institutional capacity to support experimental or place-based approaches. On the **business** side, many SMEs and cooperatives (as well as entrepreneurs) face systemic barriers in transforming bio-based side-streams into viable products or services, due to a lack of investment, poor access to infrastructure, and limited market knowledge and visibility for sustainable solutions. These issues are particularly pronounced in peripheral or island regions, where entrepreneurial ecosystems are weak or underdeveloped.

BlueRev's pilot regions (Denmark/Greenland, Estonia, Italy) reflect these shared struggles, while also highlighting the need for **context-sensitive, integrated models** that can support social, governance, and business innovation in a coherent and mutually reinforcing way. A key challenge lies in moving beyond fragmented interventions toward **replicable frameworks and tools** that address these dimensions together—creating the conditions for systemic change and sustainable regional development.

4.1.2 Asset Description

KER1 brings together four interrelated deliverables — **D3.3 (KPI and toolset)**, **D4.1 (Social Innovation Models)**, **D4.2 (Sustainable Business Models)**, and **D4.3 (Governance Recommendations)** — into an integrated package that offers both conceptual frameworks and actionable tools.

Drawing from real-world pilot cases, the models were structured around shared challenges and opportunities, reflecting both territorial specificity and broader policy relevance:

- **D3.3** introduces a KPI framework based on four pillars: Environmental Footprint, Social Innovation, Governance, and Sustainable Business Models. It is accompanied by a curated toolkit including participatory (e.g. workshops, Living Labs), analytical (e.g. Life Cycle Assessment, Material Flow Analysis), and decision-support tools (e.g. MCDA, GIS, blockchain for traceability). Together, the indicators and tools provide a robust foundation for assessing, comparing, and adapting valorisation methods in diverse pilot contexts
- **D4.1** presents tested **social innovation models**—such as Collective Impact, Community-Based Innovation, and Negotiated Governance—co-created in BlueRev pilot regions. These models are designed to support transitions toward responsible behavior and sustainable production systems, based on approaches such as **Collective Impact, Living Labs, Community-Based Innovation, and Negotiated Governance**. The models promote collaborative stakeholder engagement, value creation from underused resources (e.g., algae, fish by-products), and knowledge co-creation and emphasize behavioral change, local ownership, and inclusive participation across the value chain.

The Social Acceptability Factors addressed in the deliverable: Motivations driving stakeholders to engage in social innovation within the blue bioeconomy. Reasons for continued commitment to sustainable practices, reflecting factors that influence long-term engagement.

- **D4.2** offers a portfolio of business models designed using the **Sustainable Business Model Canvas (SBMC)**, tailored to the specific ecological and market contexts of pilot regions. The SBMC integrates value creation with environmental and social responsibility. These include innovations in side-stream valorization, nutrient recovery, algae-based products, and marine nutraceuticals.
- **D4.3** delivers governance recommendations structured around six innovation system functions (Knowledge development and dissemination; Direction of search; Resource mobilization; Market formation; Legitimacy creation; Entrepreneurial experimentation) with foresight and back casting methodologies, promoting future visioning and policy learning. The recommendations are designed to guide public and private actors in building innovation ecosystems that are collaborative, inclusive, and regionally adapted to guide regional strategies and multi-actor cooperation.

Together, these assets provide a comprehensive toolbox for developing place-based, sustainable, and scalable innovations in the blue economy.

4.1.3 Stakeholders Targeted and Expected Benefits

The deliverables are based on the real-life activities performed with the stakeholders in the hubs; their involvement was precious to shape and test the models. Starting from their profiles, we can state that this KER is designed for a wide range of stakeholders engaged in the transition toward sustainable blue economies, which are summarized in the table below (Table 2):

	SMEs, fisheries	Regional/local governments	Research centers and universities	Communities and civil society	Policy makers and regulators
Overall Role	Valorise side-streams and develop circular ventures	Align governance frameworks with sustainable development goals	Apply models in real-life scenarios or as teaching resources	Contribute to inclusive development and innovation processes	Support evidence-based transition policies
D3.3	Access to KPI-based assessment tools for method validation and business planning	Support toolkits for co-creation and decision-making in regional innovation	Evaluation frameworks for pilot replication and teaching	Participation in workshops and training, community knowledge integration	Guidance for monitoring, funding alignment, and regulatory improvement
D4.1	Enhanced value creation from underused marine resources; tools for social innovation	Increased capacity to support stakeholder engagement models	Use of co-designed models for curriculum, training, and collaborative research	Empowerment of marginalised actors (e.g., women, youth, small-scale fishers); creation of local jobs and training pathways	Frameworks to foster participatory governance and multi-level coordination
D4.2	New income streams from side-stream valorisation; collaboration to innovate, support and access to niche markets (e.g., algae, omega-3)	Tools to boost local circular economy performance; links to SDGs and Smart Specialisation	Industry collaboration for testing sustainable models; access to real-life data	Improved stewardship of marine resources; community benefits from the circular economy	Models for policy-aligned entrepreneurship and investment-readiness

D4.3	Better access to R&D, funding for valorisation, and simplified policy guidance	Multi-level governance tools; strategies for stakeholder coordination	Strengthened academia–industry collaboration; improved research impact	Preservation of cultural identity, enhanced social capital, and regional cohesion	Clearer pathways for legitimacy building, governance improvement, and innovation-driven growth
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Table 2: Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits for KER 1

4.1.4 Unique Selling Point

The strength of this KER lies in its coherence, adaptability, and transferability. Unlike isolated tools or policy guides, the BlueRev models and KPIs are interlinked and grounded in real-world experimentation across four diverse pilot regions. Their modular structure enables flexible application across various processes, including training and co-creation, as well as business planning and policy development. Each component builds on territorial knowledge, participatory design, and scientific rigor, resulting in an asset that not only supports innovation but also embeds it within locally relevant governance and business ecosystems. Further details for each deliverable are given below:

- **D3.3:** unlike generic sustainability assessment tools, the BlueRev D3.3 is tailored specifically to the **real-world complexity of the blue bioeconomy**, integrating both qualitative and quantitative dimensions. Its modular structure allows it to be **adapted to specific territorial, governance, and market conditions**, ensuring usability across regions. Additionally, the toolkit explicitly bridges the gap between **environmental performance and enabling conditions**, offering an innovative combination of **co-creation tools, systemic analysis, and market-readiness assessment** that is not found in standard frameworks.
- **D4.1:** the models described in D4.1 are **place-based, co-designed, and action-oriented**, blending scientific knowledge with local cultural and economic realities. Their strength lies in their **adaptive structure**, enabling replication and customization across different socio-ecological contexts. Furthermore, they embed **self-reflexivity mechanisms**, ensuring continuous feedback and responsiveness to stakeholder input, and make concrete use of existing value chains (e.g., eco-bottarga in Sicily or dog food valorization in Greenland), demonstrating the **economic potential of sustainable innovation** at the community level.
- **D4.2:** the set of business models has a **dual focus on sustainability and localization**. Each model is tailored to the socio-economic and ecological realities of the pilot region while offering **modular, scalable concepts** that can be adapted to other European contexts. By applying the SBMC (Sustainable Business Model Canvas) framework in real stakeholder co-creation workshops, the models are grounded in practical feasibility and community input. They span

a broad range of sectors—nutraceuticals, cosmetics, aquaculture, and energy symbiosis—and directly address emerging EU priorities such as food security, climate neutrality, and circular economy.

- **D4.3:** this governance asset has **localized, multi-actor, and replicable** nature. It blends system-level policy design with grassroots-level knowledge, including hands-on case studies (e.g. *Ritunnu Salato* in Sicily; fish skin dog treats in Greenland; circular protein valorization in Denmark; algae-based cosmetics in Estonia). Unlike top-down policy blueprints, this asset is rooted in real governance practice and experimentation. It provides practical, context-sensitive recommendations and lays the foundation for transfer to similar coastal contexts across Europe.

4.1.5 Report of Exploitation activities already carried out

The foresight method for the governance models (described in D4.3), the business model (described in D4.2) and the social innovation measures (described in D4.1), were applied during the hubs' co-creation workshops (WP4 and described in D4.4), as one of the initial step for sustainable business model development, ensuring a cohesive and supportive framework while assessing the potential for replicating successful business models across different European regions with similar resources and challenges.

The Sustainable Business Model Canvas (SBMC) developed and adapted within BlueRev (described in D4.2) has been used during the hubs' co-creation activities (WP4) as described in D4.4, and demonstration workshops (WP5) as described in chapter 5. In addition to that, the SBMC is already in active use at EMU and UNIPA regular academic curricula (Master and PhD levels) for entrepreneurship and innovation courses (academic year 2024/2025) and for professional training activities; the courses will remain a core methodological reference in teaching and applied research activities beyond academic year 2025/2026.

The SBMC framework is being reused by EMU and UNIPA in regional bioeconomy projects in Saaremaa (Estonia) and Sicily during stakeholder seminars and regional authorities workshops in Estonia and Sicily as reference frameworks for regional bioeconomy strategies.

4.1.6 Exploitation And Sustainability Recommendations

After the end of the project, the four deliverables representing KER1 will continue to be used by several consortium partners in education, research, and policy-support contexts.

Each deliverable owner (UIA, NIBIO, RISE) will upload the deliverable on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) and on the Knowledge Valorization Platform to ensure further exploitation by other interested consortia within one month after the official approval.

In addition to that, NIBIO plans to reuse the systematic report on KPI framework developed in D3.3 in future research activities and Horizon Europe proposals related to circular bioeconomy and Living Labs, building on the methodological work carried out in BlueRev.

In the following table, partners detailed the past and future exploitation of this KER (Table 3):

PARTNER	EXPLOITATION ROUTES AND ACTION PLAN
1- APRE	No specific action plan has been established for this KER other than guaranteeing the upload on the appropriate EU platform as soon as possible to inspire future research and projects. APRE will reference these models in proposal development support activities for stakeholders, preparing Horizon Europe applications in the bioeconomy and regional innovation domains.
2- FBCD	Using results to support decision-makers in designing a new/improved regulatory framework and meeting the Greenlandic government's desire to engage everyone in society in participating in the transition to a more sustainable and self-sufficient Greenland. ⁴
3- DFBG	No specific action plan
4- LOBA	No specific action plan
5- UIA	Upload D4.2 on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) and on the Knowledge Valorization Platform within one month after the official approval.
6- RISE	Upload D4.3 on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) and on the Knowledge Valorization Platform within one month after the official approval.
7- EMU	The novel business, social and governance models and their development methodology (e.g. SBMC) from the project have been integrated into the training and courses developed by the EMU, and those will be further used after the end of the project. The recommendations from D4.3. will be used in the annual bioeconomy seminars organized by the EMU for the public sector and industry. The data collected on the models will be utilized in the ongoing PhD project in EMU, including for the publications after the end of the project. The project results on the models and related research methodology will be integrated into the new research projects and proposals for Horizon Europe calls on bioeconomy, innovation, and Living Labs.
8- NIBIO	Upload D3.3 and D4.1 on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) and on the Knowledge Valorization Platform within one month after the official approval.
9- UNIPA	UNIPA proposes to use KERs as an example of approach both in future educational programmes and in specific professional training courses in the field of blue growth, but also to strengthen collaboration and synergy with local institutional partners, seeking to translate the guidelines

⁴ [New paths for the fishing industry's side streams](#)

outlined by Bluerev into lasting actions in the region (i.e. Scaling Living Lab for local innovation)

Table 3: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 1

4.2 KER2: Guidelines reporting the best practices demonstrated in pilot regions D4.4

4.2.1 Challenge

The blue bioeconomy offers immense opportunities to transform marine biological resources into sustainable products. However, the sector faces major challenges in identifying, scaling, and replicating effective business, governance, and social innovation models.

For example, most local actors operate in fragmented environments and SMEs often lack the tools, visibility, and support to valorise underutilised marine resources.

Regulatory barriers, fragmented markets, and limited access to finance further complicate the creation of sustainable value chains. This hinders knowledge transfer and slows systemic change.

BlueRev sought to bridge these gaps by co-creating regionally tailored best practices that are both innovative and practical, with replicable models of success.

4.2.2 Asset Description

Deliverable D4.4 synthesises the outcomes of stakeholder-driven co-creation processes conducted in Denmark/Greenland, Estonia, and Sicily, and offers a best practice guideline aimed at supporting the replication of sustainable business models based on blue bioeconomy models. The document provides step-by-step guidance using the SBMC, enriched with concrete case studies, such as omega-3 nutrition drinks in Denmark; dog food from fish processing side streams in Greenland; algae-based nutraceuticals and cosmetics in Estonia; marine by-product transformation & valorisation in Italy, with the case of the sustainable valorisation of underutilized fishery species (i.e. *Ritunnu salato*). It integrates dimensions of social innovation, governance, and business into a comprehensive roadmap for local actors seeking to replicate and adapt these models.

SBMC was further elaborated and graphically adapted to be a stand-alone document, and a useful guideline for implementing a Sustainable Business, independently of the sector.

4.2.3 Stakeholders Targeted and Expected Benefits

The D4.4 was shaped with the insights coming from all the interviews and the co-creation workshops in WP3 and WP4, using real data and elaborating them in a structured way.

Analyzing the type of stakeholder that were actively involved and that are listed in the deliverable, we can foresee that a wide range of stakeholders can benefit from this KER: the examples provided and the explanation of each of them divided into simple paragraphs (Social and environmental impact; Implementation Guidelines; Key To-Dos for Stakeholders; Scaling and replicability) make them easier to follow and reproduce in other similar context. A summary is provided in the table below (Table 4):

	SMEs, fisheries	Regional/local governments	Research centers and universities	Communities and civil society	Policy makers and regulators
D4.4	Invest and collaborate in innovation to optimize product portfolio by exploring by-product applications and value chain development sustainably, integrating and appreciating traditions and environmental concerns	Provide tailored regulations to support local products, enhance resource efficiency and expand markets	Offer R&D support to improve product shelf-life and quality control; Tackle technical challenges in production and scale up and collaborate with industry to create innovative solutions for ecological and logistical challenges	Leverage the social innovation elements to engage citizens and preserve cultural heritage, while simultaneously contributing to local development and sustainability goals	Create a supportive regulatory framework and offer financial incentives or grants to increase local welfare, increasing job opportunities

Table 4: Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits for KER 2

4.2.4 Unique Selling Point

The D4.4 guideline has an integrated approach, combining real-life business case studies with a structured framework for implementation and scaling. It offers tools and step-by-step guidelines not only for designing blue bio-based business models but also for embedding them within appropriate governance and social innovation systems. The document ensures practical applicability and adaptability to different socio-economic and environmental contexts.

The paragraph on “Successful Approaches” described can be inspirational for other coastal communities; it presents key findings from co-creation workshops across pilot regions and shares actionable recommendations and practical advice for scaling the identified best practices in the blue bioeconomy.

4.2.5 Report of Exploitation activities already carried out

The SBMC has been used during the hubs’ co-creation activities (WP4) as described in D4.4, and demonstration workshops (WP5) as described in chapter 5; during workshops performed in Greenland, several fish producers recognized that best case depicted in the report, the “*Ritunnu* case” study, could be replicated within their coastal region using local fishes and following the procedures described.

FBCD, that provides services to companies and organisations on innovation, internationalisation, investment, funding, incubation and networking along the entire food and bioeconomy value chain, is already using the deliverable to inspire local SMEs on how to apply the models described, and the model will be maintained also for the future.

UIA is currently using the step-by-step recommendation through scholarly channels and research community networks for methodological demonstrations, applied research activities and broader knowledge sharing, and plans to reuse the framework in future research activities and Horizon Europe proposals.

4.2.6 Exploitation And Sustainability Recommendations

After the end of the project, the best-practice guidelines collected in D4.4 will be reused by consortium partners as a reference for replication and advisory activities in the blue bioeconomy. In fact, the deliverable represents a starting point to explore market opportunities and to define the necessary steps towards enhanced sustainability and economic resilience.

UNIPA and EMU will reuse the guidelines in educational and professional training programmes and in collaboration with local institutional partners (academic year 2024/2025) and beyond 2025.

In the following table, partners detailed the past and future exploitation of this KER (Table 5):

PARTNER	EXPLOITATION ROUTES AND ACTION PLAN
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1- APRE	No specific action plan has been established for this KER other than guaranteeing the upload on the appropriate EU platform to inspire future research and projects.
2- FBCD	Use of the best practices described in the document to support local SMEs in pushing forward their new sustainable value chains
3- DFBG	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
4- LOBA	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
5- UIA	Upload D4.4 on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) and on the Knowledge Valorization Platform within one month after the official approval, to ensure further exploitation by other interested consortia. Use of the information and the recommendation through scholarly channels and research community networks for broader knowledge sharing.
6- RISE	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
7- EMU	The Estonian translation of recommendations will be used for methodological demonstration (SBMC and governance canvas) for future applied projects on the regional bioeconomy strategies and policy assessments, and for teaching methods development. The EMU faculty study circles on teaching methodology will discuss the use of SBMC for entrepreneurship courses and the adoption of canvases for student projects at the meeting in Fall 2025. The D4.4. recommendations have been disseminated and used among the EMU faculty and Saaremaa regional stakeholders, including SMEs and the local Kuressaare College, which will integrate the materials (BlueRev case studies and methodologies) into its new BA program of Sustainable Technologies in the Blue Economy.
8- NIBIO	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
9- UNIPA	UNIPA proposes to use KERs as an example of an approach both in future educational programmes and in specific professional training courses in the field of blue growth, but also to strengthen collaboration and synergy with local institutional partners, seeking to translate the guidelines outlined by BlueRev into lasting actions in the region

Table 5: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 2

4.3 KER3: Training programme and materials D5.1, D5.2

4.3.1 Challenge

One key obstacle in unlocking the potential of the blue bioeconomy lies in the mismatch between emerging opportunities and the availability of suitably trained professionals. Coastal regions, while rich in marine resources, often lack the technical expertise, entrepreneurial capacity, and communication skills necessary to develop high-value bio-based solutions. BlueRev recognized that without targeted capacity-building, even the most innovative ideas risk stagnation. The project responded by designing a modular

training programme that bridges the knowledge gap across education, industry, and governance, adapting to the unique needs of local actors in Denmark/Greenland, Estonia, and Italy.

4.3.2 Asset Description

The set of training described in D5.1 and D5.2 provided by the consortium and available in the project web tool sets out a multi-level training strategy, offering tailored content across four thematic modules: from marine by-product valorisation and sustainable business development to consumer communication and governance models. This asset draws directly from stakeholder needs identified in earlier phases of the project (WP3 & WP4) and integrates local case studies and TRL-validated processes (e.g., omega-3 extraction, chitin valorisation). The programme includes online webinars, classroom sessions, and downloadable materials, ensuring both flexibility and durability. Notably, the training was designed with both horizontal (cross-sector) and vertical (from vocational to PhD level) applicability in mind, forming a scalable learning resource for Europe's blue economy transition.

4.3.3 Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits

The training programme addresses a dual audience. On one hand, it equips local producers, small enterprises, and associations with practical tools to diversify their operations, reduce waste, and increase product value. On the other hand, it supports the next generation of researchers and professionals by embedding blue bioeconomy topics into academic curricula, thereby fostering skills development and career opportunities within emerging blue careers.

This KER is designed for a wide range of stakeholders engaged in the transition toward sustainable blue economies, which are summarized in the table below:

	SMEs, fisheries	Regional/local governments	Research centers and universities	Communities and civil society	Policy makers and regulators
D5.1; D5.2	To diversify their operations, reduce waste, and increase product value	Identification and better understanding of regional prospects and shortcomings, local stakeholders' needs for regional growth, and improved capacity to engage and	Replicable content to be used in training courses	Improved capacity to advocate for coastal communities' needs and contribute to local development and policy making, and solutions	Improved understanding and knowledge of the technological shifts, innovation barriers, and need for support, and the policy impacts, enhancing the

		support the local stakeholders			quality of policy-making
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Table 6: Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits for KER 3

4.3.4 Unique Selling Point

What distinguishes the training program is its deep integration of hands-on technical knowledge (e.g., green extraction methods, analytical chemistry, circular value chains) with strategic foresight (e.g., SDG alignment, European green deal; zero-waste strategy; entrepreneurial mindset, consumer trust-building). Rather than offering generic training, the programme is tightly coupled with BlueRev’s pilot activities and value chains, ensuring relevance. Its hybrid delivery format and open-access online repository increase longevity and inclusivity, while alignment with educational structures (e.g., bachelor’s and PhD tracks) guarantees institutional anchoring beyond the life of the project.

4.3.5 Report of Exploitation activities already carried out

EMU and UNIPA have integrated their training modules into Master’s and PhD-level courses and dedicated innovation training programmes for the academic year 2024/2025; UNIPA has used the materials in professional courses, and digital academy initiatives within the FORTHEM alliance.

EMU has also used the training programs and video materials developed by the UNIPA in various departments for innovation courses, university-wide bioeconomy courses, and in specialized courses on blue bioresource use. The training materials have also been shared with the local Estonian College in the pilot region to be used as training materials, including for the Sustainable Technologies in Blue Economy BA program at the college, and for further use among the SMEs and other stakeholders in the pilot region.

4.3.6 Exploitation And Sustainability Recommendations

To ensure continued impact, BlueRev proposes embedding this training programme into existing bioeconomy education in the universities of reference.

From the following academic year 2025/2026 onwards, the BlueRev training programme and materials will be further exploited by several partners through formal education and professional training activities. EMU will integrate the training modules into Master’s and PhD-level courses and dedicated innovation training programmes, while UNIPA will reuse the materials in university teaching for master’s and PhD students, professional courses, and digital academy initiatives within the FORTHEM alliance.

FBCD and APRE will support the dissemination and visibility of the training materials through EU knowledge platforms, ensuring continued access for external users. The table below presents the partner-specific exploitation routes planned after the project end.

In the following table, partners detailed the past and future exploitation of this KER:

PARTNER	EXPLOITATION ROUTES AND ACTION PLAN
1- APRE	No specific action plan has been established for this KER other than guaranteeing the upload on the appropriate EU platform to inspire future research and projects.
2- FBCD	Upload of D5.1 on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) and the Knowledge Valorization Platform within one month after the official approval.
3- DFBG	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
4- LOBA	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
5- UIA	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
6- RISE	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
7- EMU	<p>The exploitation plan for this KER includes the further use of the sustainable innovation modules and training materials developed by the EMU for courses for the master's and PhD students and for industry training. After the end of the project, the modules developed in the project will be offered as a full course of Sustainable innovation in blue bioeconomy in the academic year 2025/2026; and as part of an innovation module for PhD students in spring 2026 and in the subsequent academic years. The training will also be adopted for a standalone, intensive, international short-term sustainable innovation course for Master students in the spring of 2026 in the Baltic Forestry, Veterinary and Agricultural University Network (BOVA UN).</p> <p>The social innovation module will be used as part of regular training programs EMU offers to SMEs in the rural tourism network in 2026 and 2027.</p> <p>The training programs and video materials, including those developed by the UNIPA, have been shared with faculty from various departments within EMU for use in innovation courses, university-wide bioeconomy courses, and in specialized courses on blue bioresource use. The training materials have also been shared with the local Kuressaare College in the pilot region to be used as training materials, including for the Sustainable Technologies in Blue Economy BA program at the college, and for further use among the SMEs and other stakeholders in the pilot region.</p>
8- NIBIO	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
9- UNIPA	The university will leverage this KER to incorporate the knowledge into potential new training programs and broaden its educational offerings; furthermore, UNIPA will include its training in the digital academy

	<p>program, within the FORTHEM universities alliance. This opportunity will multiply the beneficial effects of the training in the European blue growth community.</p> <p>Upload of D5.3 on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) and on the Knowledge Valorization Platform within one month after the official approval.</p>
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Table 7: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 3

4.4 KER4: Guidelines supporting the development of communication of innovation D5.4

4.4.1 Challenge

One challenge in the blue bioeconomy lies in transforming knowledge and innovation into actionable communication strategies for small businesses and effective communication remains a barrier for blue bio-based SMEs seeking to enter the market or scale up. Although the sector shows growing potential in terms of sustainability, circularity, and socio-economic development, many SMEs struggle to translate the scientific and technological value of their products into clear, effective messages; many actors lack the knowledge or tools to convey their innovations clearly to consumers, funders, or policy audiences. Poor messaging undermines impact and slows the transition toward a circular blue economy.

BlueRev addressed this gap by identifying and analysing best practices in communication to support the uptake of sustainable blue bio-based solutions. The project highlighted the importance of strategic communication as a tool not only for awareness raising but also for business development and consumer engagement, especially in emerging markets such as marine-derived bioactive products, algae-based applications, and fish by-product valorisation.

4.4.2 Asset Description

BlueRev produced a comprehensive set of communication guidelines specifically aimed at SMEs in the blue bioeconomy: deliverable D5.4 provides a practical guide to articulate a communication campaign, giving advice on how to communicate the environmental, economic, and social value of bio-based innovations and focussing on the innovation and building public trust.

D5.4 includes strategies for targeting diverse audiences, designing messages, selecting suitable communication channels, and evaluating communication effectiveness; the deliverable is based on the analysis of literature, stakeholder input from pilot regions (Italy, Denmark, and Estonia), and real-world case studies. The document provides a practical framework including message design, target audience segmentation, appropriate tools and channels, and monitoring strategies. It also includes examples

such as the successful promotion of *Ritunnu Salatu* in Sicily, showcasing the strategic use of storytelling, stakeholder engagement, and experiential marketing.

The deliverable was also linked to the development of 4 videos, published on the [BlueRev Support Tool](#), which illustrate key communication strategies tailored for blue bioeconomy SMEs. These videos provide practical insights into how to craft compelling narratives, engage different stakeholders, and effectively communicate the added value of bio-based innovations. They include visual storytelling examples and expert tips, making them a useful complement to the guidelines for training, awareness-raising, and capacity-building activities.

4.4.3 Stakeholders Targeted and Expected Benefits

This KER is designed for a wide range of stakeholders engaged in the transition toward sustainable blue economies, which are summarized in the Table 8 below:

	SMEs, fisheries	Regional/local governments	Research centers and universities	Communities and civil society	Policy makers and regulators
D5.4	To improve product visibility, connect with customers, and attract investment	To support the communication strategies of local bio-based clusters	A pedagogical tool in training future professionals in sustainable innovation and bioeconomy communication	A better understanding of how to convey complex scientific information to the public	Improved public engagement and outreach activities, and the enhanced ability to communicate policy intentions and the policymaking process to stakeholders

Table 8: Stakeholders Targeted And Expected Benefits for KER 4

4.4.4 Unique Selling Point

The key value of the BlueRev communication guidelines lies in their sector-specific relevance and practical orientation. Unlike generic communication handbooks, D5.4 offers a unique focus on marine bio-resources and their sustainable transformation, grounded in actual experiences from European pilot regions. The guidelines are available in 24 EU languages, ensuring broad accessibility. Their modular and flexible structure makes them adaptable across various contexts, enhancing replicability and scalability throughout the EU and beyond.

4.4.5 Report of Exploitation activities already carried out

The communication framework presented in D5.4 has been used by FBCD in SME advisory activities and training workshops, and by APRE as a reference model for communication capacity-building in new Horizon Europe projects starting in 2026. FBCD, that is already using the handbook during its core activities, will keep on exploiting it when supporting SMEs in communication-related activities.

APRE is using the guidelines and accompanying videos in capacity-building actions in other Horizon Europe projects addressing sustainability and innovation communication, not limited to the bluebioeconomy. APRE is also using the structure of the deliverable D5.4 as a base for other similar document in other projects.

EMU used the translated communication guidelines in the faculty and in the communication department for training courses covering marketing communication.

UNIPA used the guidelines for dialogue with SMEs on communication regarding products, services and the company itself.

4.4.6 Exploitation and Sustainability Recommendations

After the end of the project, the communication guidelines developed in D5.4 will continue to be used by consortium partners in training, advisory, and stakeholder engagement activities.

EMU and UNIPA will apply the guidelines in training courses and in direct dialogue with SMEs to improve communication of blue bioeconomy solutions.

In the following table, partners detailed the past and future exploitation of this KER:

PARTNER	EXPLOITATION ROUTES AND ACTION PLAN
1- APRE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upload of the Deliverable D5.4 on the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) and on the Knowledge Valorization Platform and EuBioNet network⁵ within one month after the official approval. • Cross-project Synergies: use of the deliverable and the videos for shaping trainings in ongoing and new HE projects -dealing with sustainability, circular bioeconomy, or regional innovation ecosystems- in activities related to capacity building as a best practice example. <p>Capacity Building for SMEs: Policy and Strategic Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replication in Other Sectors: Use of this communication model beyond the blue bioeconomy, in related fields facing similar messaging challenges.

⁵ [Guidelines for SMEs on Communicating Innovation and Sustainability in the Blue Bioeconomy – The European Bioeconomy Network](#)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Briefs or Recommendations: Derive policy recommendations on communication capacity-building for SMEs based on insights from the deliverable, targeting regional development agencies and innovation policymakers.
2- FBCD	Use the Communication Handbook when in dialogue with SMEs regarding communication about products, services, and the company itself.
3- DFBG	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
4- LOBA	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
5- UIA	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
6- RISE	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
7- EMU	The translated D5.4 communication guidelines has been shared within the faculty and with the communication department at EMU. The KER will be further used in training courses, including those covering marketing communication, as well as in future applied projects and workshops with SMEs to improve dialogue with the sector and to further disseminate it as a useful tool for SMEs
8- NIBIO	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
9- UNIPA	Use the D5.4 guidelines in dialogue with SME on communication regarding products, services and the company itself.

Table 9: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 4

4.5 KER5: Support Tool

4.5.1 Challenge

Stakeholders across the bio-based economy, especially SMEs, NGOs, and local actors, often face fragmented access to knowledge, limited peer-to-peer exchange opportunities, and a lack of user-friendly, sector-specific training resources. Additionally, cross-sector collaboration and capacity building are hindered by language barriers, limited digital infrastructure, and inconsistent access to relevant tools and best practices. There is a need for a centralised, interactive, and multilingual platform that enables continuous knowledge sharing, training, and stakeholder engagement to accelerate the uptake of sustainable and circular practices.

4.5.2 Asset Description

The support tool platform <https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/> is conceptualised to be an Open Space that contains materials developed within the project, including multimedia contents and demonstrative videos for best practices implemented, lessons recordings and related materials, best practices guidelines etc., and standard info i.e. project and partners, calendar of events, news, etc., by facilitating cross-sector collaborations among stakeholders in the bio-based economy and to provide a knowledge centre to share relevant project results.

The purpose of the Support Tool is to host an online space for mutual exchange, collaboration, communication, and training that will empower the stakeholders to achieve the envisioned results in their communities.

4.5.3 Stakeholders Targeted and Expected Benefits

Four types of users are expected to frequent the tool and make the best of its use: Company managers (including NGOs, Social enterprises, SMEs, fishery, and biomass sectors, etc), Policy makers, Trainees, and Project partners.

- **The users:** the users can register on the platform, create their profile, and choose and customise specific settings. The users will have access to the homepage, calendar, where they can create events, and see the upcoming webinars and training courses.
- **Community feed:** this feature allows users to interact with each other, send direct messages, choose discussion topics, and even share documents within the discussion forums.
- **E-library:** an online library where users will be able to access exclusive materials like factsheets, infographics, best practices, multimedia content, and much more.
- **Training courses and webinars:** users will be able to register, attend, and download training courses and webinars, both available in live and streaming. Each training course and webinar will allow a discussion forum where the participants may interact with other participants and the lecturer, asking questions, cross-examine facts, and share opinions.

4.5.4 Unique Selling Point

Three guidelines were created to ensure all users can use every feature in a seamless manner. They are available in the footer of the platform, as shown in the Figure 1. We are also developing video support to complement the guidelines already in place.

Figure 1: Support tool footer.

A multi-language option is planned for future implementations. We expect to be able to implement Italian, Estonian, and Dutch language options in addition to English, which is already implemented.

A help-desk support team is also in place to provide immediate support for questions and doubts users might experience when using the platform. This task will be the responsibility of LOBA which also created the platform. If necessary, a FAQs section will also be implemented in the platform to provide more information to the users.

4.5.5 Exploitation and Sustainability Recommendations

The BlueRev Support Tool is designed to remain operational beyond the project's end. From September 2025 onwards, LOBA will be responsible for maintaining the platform online and ensuring basic technical support, while consortium partners will continue to use it to upload new material as repository for training materials and guidelines. The log-in feature will be eliminated to increase the useability of the tool.

EMU and UNIPA will disseminate the platform to students, researchers, and local stakeholders and will reuse it to host and access new training content. APRE will contribute to the visibility of the platform within EU-level dissemination and knowledge-sharing activities.

In the following table, partners detailed the possible future exploitation of this KER:

PARTNER	EXPLOITATION ROUTES AND ACTION PLAN
1- APRE	No specific action plan has been established for this KER other than guaranteeing the upload on the appropriate EU platform to inspire future research and projects.
2- FBCD	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
3- DFBG	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
4- LOBA	LOBA will maintain online the support tool (as well as the website) for the next 5 years, but the content development and expansion will be open to the participants. Editor rights will be provided to designated members of the consortium, and should more funds be acquired for the expansion of the support tool LOBA is available to work on it. The log-in feature will be eliminated to increase the useability of the tool
5- UIA	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
6- RISE	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
7- EMU	The information on the support tool and its materials will be disseminated to the local stakeholders and within EMU and other research institutions also after the end of the project, to provide access to useful training and information materials for the sector and for faculty for further utilization of the training materials in their courses and use it to further develop and test their new training ideas and methodologies.
8- NIBIO	No specific action plan has been established for this KER
9- UNIPA	UNIPA will keep on using the platform to upload new training for students

Table 10: Exploitation routes and action plan for KER 5

4.6 Post-project exploitation at a glance

KER	Main User	Where	When	Tool / Framework Used
KER1: Novel business, governance, and social innovation models (D3.3, D4.1, D4.2, D4.3)	EMU, UNIPA, UIA, NIBIO, RISE, APRE	Estonia (EMU, NIBIO), Sicily/Italy (UNIPA), Norway (RISE), EU knowledge platforms (UIA, APRE)	From September 2025 onwards	KPI framework (D3.3), Sustainable Business Model Canvas (D4.2), Social Innovation Models (D4.1), Governance recommendations (D4.3)
KER2: Guidelines reporting best practices (D4.4)	UIA, EMU, FBCD, UNIPA, APRE	Denmark/Greenland (FBCD), Estonia (EMU), Italy/Sicily (UNIPA), EU knowledge platforms (APRE)	From September 2025 onwards	Best practice guidelines, SBMC
KER3: Training programme and materials (D5.1, D5.2, D5.3)	EMU, UNIPA, FBCD, APRE	Estonia (EMU), Italy/Sicily (UNIPA), local SMEs (FBCD), EU knowledge platforms (APRE)	Academic year 2025/2026 onwards	Training modules, webinars, online materials, video recordings
KER4: Guidelines supporting communication of innovation (D5.4)	APRE, EMU, UNIPA, FBCD	Italy/Sicily (UNIPA), Estonia (EMU), Greenland (FBCD), EU knowledge platforms (APRE)	From September 2025 onwards	Communication guidelines, instructional videos
KER5: Support Tool (online platform)	LOBA, EMU, UNIPA, APRE	Online platform: https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/ ; Estonia (EMU), Italy/Sicily (UNIPA), EU (APRE)	From September 2025 onwards	BlueRev Support Tool platform hosting guidelines, training materials, videos, best practices

5 Report On Exploitation Activities Already Carried Out

The deliverables and knowledge resources developed and outlined in Chapter 4 played a central role in supporting the stakeholder workshops conducted across the four regional hubs—Italy, Denmark, Greenland, and Estonia. These materials were the basis for developing and validating the recommendations that emerged from local engagement processes. The content served as a reference framework during discussions with stakeholders, ensuring that the recommendations were grounded in the scientific and technical work carried out by the project. Additional description is given in the following paragraphs (5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4).

These outputs were actively integrated into the project's capacity-building efforts, particularly within the training program of Work Package 5 (WP5). Specifically, they were incorporated into Deliverables (especially D5.1 and D5.3- KER 2 in Table 1), which focused on building skills and awareness among key actors.

Beyond textual and training materials, the project produced additional communication tools to enhance accessibility and engagement. Three videos, each representing key findings from other projects' hubs, were developed to visually communicate the outcomes and regional perspectives. Furthermore, seven fact sheets were created to summarize complex project outputs in a clear and visually appealing format, making them suitable for both expert and non-expert audiences. These visual materials were widely distributed at the final BlueRev event and are also permanently available on the project webpage (D5.2)⁶.

An important asset in extending the reach and visibility of BlueRev was the active involvement of a **Young Ocean Advocate** within the consortium. This figure acted as a liaison with the **Youth4Ocean Forum** and the **EU4Ocean Coalition**, effectively tapping into a broader network of young professionals, activists, and community leaders engaged in ocean literacy and sustainability across Europe. Through this connection, BlueRev outputs were shared with youth networks, presented in European-level events, and promoted through various communication campaigns. This not only enhanced the project's outreach and engagement potential, particularly among younger audiences, but also fostered synergies with other EU-funded initiatives, contributing to the overall visibility and legacy of the project.

Moreover, these materials were made publicly accessible via multiple dissemination channels, including the BlueRev website, the online platform, and the Zenodo open-access repository⁷. Their visibility and reach are documented in Table 11, which provides figures on the number of downloads and views, serving as concrete indicators of the exploitation and uptake of project results. The statistics are available only for the already

⁶ 10.5281/zenodo.15878312

⁷ Zenodo: [Search Bio-based revitalisation of local communities](#)

accepted and public deliverables, that are visible on Zenodo (statistic of 29/08/2025). Table 11 complements the stakeholder engagement metrics reported in *D2.2- Report on number of stakeholders engaged*⁸, by providing **centralised evidence of external uptake**, measured through views and downloads of publicly available deliverables on Zenodo.

NAME	DOI	Views	Downloads
D1.3 DMP update	10.5281/zenodo.14065259	68	58
D2.1 Stakeholders' board structure, communication tools and rules	10.5281/zenodo.7378172	57	25
D3.1 Framework for mapping	10.5281/zenodo.14135371	105	57
D3.2 Dataset	10.5281/zenodo.14135095	56	44
D3.5 LCA report on the pilot regions	10.5281/zenodo.14039573	71	48
D3.4 Analysis of governance models in the pilot regions	10.5281/zenodo.10617209	78	32
D3.6 Business models	10.5281/zenodo.14039973	72	76
D6.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities	10.5281/zenodo.7682336	100	43
D6.2 Updated plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities	10.5281/zenodo.10604265	44	28
Scientific publication: Valorization of the Invasive Blue Crabs (<i>Callinectes sapidus</i>) in the Mediterranean: Nutritional Value, Bioactive Compounds and Sustainable By-Products Utilization	10.3390/md22090430	17	12
Scientific publication: In Vitro Potential of Antioxidant Extracts from <i>Gracilaria gracilis</i> Cultivated in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) for Marine Biobased Sector	10.3390/w16182667	31	75

⁸ 10.5281/zenodo.15877580

Scientific publication: "From Sea to Sustainability: Transitioning the Blue Bioeconomy through Responsible Design Thinking and the Sustainable Business Model Canvas"	https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5e8f3c880e1d607ebd5469b6/t/686262ac5a2ec41778843eb8/1751278266376/Book+of+Abstract_haskolaprent_June+23_Final.pdf	/	/
Proceedings of the XXXVI ISPIM Innovation Conference. The International Society for Professional Innovation Management – ISBN 978-952-65069-9-9	https://conferencesubmissions.com/ispim/bergen2025/index.html	/	/
Scientific publication: Mapping the governance landscape of the blue bioeconomy: A systems approach to understanding innovation barriers and enablers.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2025.107899	/	/
Publication: Science Communication through Engagement and Outreach for the bioeconomy	Abstract EGU25-7084	/	/
Scientific publication: Systemic changes in Practice: Exploring Transformative Social Innovations in the Marine Food Systems in Trapani	Submitted but not public yet	/	/
Scientific publication: Photoprotective and Anti-Melanogenic Effects of Supercritical Fluids Extract from Posidonia oceanica Beach-Cast Leaves: From Waste Stream to Cosmeceutical Applications	https://zenodo.org/records/18242348 https://www.mdpi.com/1660-3397/24/1/27#Funding	/	/

Table 11: Zenodo statistics

5.1 Validation and transfer of new solutions: Italian HUB

5.1.1 Introduction

The Italian pilot region organised a demonstration workshop on 29 May 2025 at the Polo Territoriale di Trapani (Conference Room, *Complesso Principe di Napoli*, Via Cappuccini 7, Trapani, Italy). The initiative was coordinated by the scientific partner DiSTeM –

University of Palermo (UNIPA), with the technical support of the District of the Fishery and Blue Growth (DFBG).

The workshop aimed to present, validate and discuss the innovative, transferable solutions developed within the project by the Italian pilot, to support the development of a sustainable blue bioeconomy at a local level. The event provided a platform for the exchange of practical knowledge, stakeholder engagement and the collaborative development of strategies across academia, industry, institutions and civil society. The workshop program featured a mix of interactive presentations, panel discussions and case-based demonstrations, structured to:

- Showcase replicable case studies and high-TRL solutions developed in Sicily that could be applied in other European coastal areas;
- Share practical tools, methodologies and outputs produced in the HUB during the BlueRev project;
- Foster the co-creation of inclusive, locally anchored blue growth strategies;
- Strengthen multi-actor collaboration and networking at regional and European levels.

The broad and diverse participation ensured a dynamic environment for multi-level dialogue, knowledge sharing and collaborative solution building, fully in line with the strategic objectives of the BlueRev project.

5.1.2 Case study context

The workshop focused on the Italian pilot case study in Trapani, a coastal area in western Sicily with a long tradition of fisheries, aquaculture, and the processing sector. The local economy and culture have always been linked to the sea, with fishing and aquaculture playing a vital role in providing livelihoods and driving regional development.

The Italian pilot case study aimed to develop and validate a replicable and scalable value chain model based on sustainability, technological innovation, and community engagement. A key part of this approach was to add value to fishery and aquaculture by-products, which are typically considered waste, by transforming them into valuable products using circular economy strategies combined with innovative, bio-based technologies. This includes extracting bioactive compounds for use in various industries.

By promoting local entrepreneurship and adopting inclusive governance frameworks, the pilot demonstrated how an integrated strategy can effectively strengthen the socio-economic resilience of coastal communities. In this way, the Trapani case study serves as a model for disseminating blue bio-economy solutions that can support sustainable growth in other Mediterranean and European coastal regions.

The strategic relevance of the Trapani case study is further enhanced by the region's rich marine biodiversity, existing infrastructure, and strong knowledge base. This makes the region an ideal test bed for implementing innovative approaches to managing marine resources, diversifying the economy, and fostering social inclusion within the broader blue economy framework.

5.1.3 Activities

The full-day workshop took place on 29 May 2025 at the *Complesso Principe di Napoli* in Trapani and featured a structured programme. The event was organised and facilitated by a multi-actor team led by UNIPA as Scientific Coordinator. The event adopted a mixed methodology, combining presentations of project results and good practices at the regional level, thematic sessions and round tables with multi-sectoral stakeholders to stimulate Interactive dialogue and networking moments, panel discussions and case sharing (real-world examples supported peer learning and the contextualization of project strategies).

➤ Morning session

The workshop opened with institutional welcomes from representatives of the University of Palermo, including the President, Pro Rector for Research and Technology Transfer, and Department Director. Additional welcomes were given by representatives of the Fisheries Department of the Sicily Region, and Sicindustria Trapani, the local industry association. These addresses underline the regional commitment to fostering sustainable development and innovation in the blue economy.

Session 1 – Solutions for social sustainability: Chaired by Giovanna Ottaviani (NIBIO) and Marita Bustamante Liria (NIBIO), this session explored innovative social models aimed at promoting sustainability in marine-based production systems. The session opened with a presentation on the methodology and key findings of the Social Innovation pillar of the BlueRev project, emphasizing participatory approaches and community empowerment. A key highlight was the presentation of the “Living Lab SMART” by Prof. Concetta Messina (UNIPA). This initiative was presented as a replicable model of community-led innovation, promoting the development of local marine food systems.

Session 2 – Solutions for business models in biobased production (OP Trapani, Beehive Valore Sud, DFBG): Chaired by Prof. Concetta Messina (UNIPA) and Prof Bjerne Tore Flaten (University of Agder, UiA), this session explored innovative business models aimed at strengthening the blue bioeconomy. Natale Amoroso, President of the Trapani Fish Producers' Organisation, presented a case study on the production of fish meal from sustainable marine resources (*ritunnu salato*), highlighting its potential to improve both environmental sustainability and economic performance in the fisheries sector. Gianfranco Incandela of Beehive Valore Sud introduced a capacity-building and knowledge-sharing model focused on empowering start-ups and young entrepreneurs, demonstrating how collaborative platforms can drive local innovation. Antonino Vincenzo Carlino, President of the District of Fisheries and Blue Growth (DFBG), concluded the session with an overview of the district's strategic initiatives to promote regional cooperation, enterprise development, and innovation in the blue economy, reinforcing Trapani's role as a reference point for sustainable marine-based value chains. His talk was implemented by the intervention of the enterprise Siciliana fish represented by Natalie Rallo.

Session 3 – Innovative governance for sustainable blue economy: This session addressed the crucial governance frameworks for supporting sustainable enterprises and community-driven initiatives. Professor Concetta Messina presented the Community of Practice model, which promotes cooperation between research, education and social innovation to support sustainable resource management.

Session 4 – Training and coaching for blue biotech careers and networking: This session focused on enhancing employment opportunities in the blue biotechnology sector and reinforcing international cooperation through education and training. Capacity-building initiatives were showcased, designed to equip participants with skills that align with the evolving needs of the blue bioeconomy. Simona Manuguerra (UNIPA) presented the BlueRev training courses aimed at developing key competences in blue biotechnology, emphasising their crucial role in equipping participants with specialised skills and fostering the professional development of young talent and aspiring entrepreneurs in the blue economy sector. Marta Ferrantelli explained how the Europe Direct Trapani Centre connects local stakeholders with EU-level networks, funding opportunities and collaborative platforms, thereby strengthening the Trapani region's international visibility and integration. Finally, Prof. Concetta Messina (UNIPA) introduced Prof Vincenzo Todaro, coordinator of the FORTHEM Alliance, who introduced the Blended Intensive Programme (BIP) on Mediterranean foods, cultural diversity, and migration. This programme exemplifies how transnational cooperation among European universities can foster inclusive educational models and promote sustainable development in Mediterranean coastal regions, also in marginalized groups.

➤ Afternoon session

Regional good practices and European collaboration (Engage4Bio, CelltoFood, MEDIET4ALL, AGCI, and WestMED): This session showcased exemplary initiatives led or supported by the regional BlueRev HUB, demonstrating how the UNIPA team, thanks to the multi-stakeholder collaboration, can advance sustainable innovation in the blue economy. Eleonora Curcuraci (UNIPA) presented the Engage4Bio project, which fosters sustainable blue economy solutions through active engagement among research institutions, educational bodies, local authorities, and businesses. The project exemplifies a territorial approach to co-creation and shared governance. Carlotta Giromini (UNIMI) and Concetta Messina (UNIPA) introduced PRIN CelltoFood, a research project on cellular agriculture. The initiative focuses on the use of marine by-products in the development of cultivated meat, aiming to reduce environmental impacts and promote circular bio-based food systems, according to the blue transformation Roadmap. Achraf Ammar (University of Mainz) discussed the MEDIET4ALL project, a transnational movement promoting a modern and sustainable Mediterranean diet. The project leverages technological innovation to reconnect communities with traditional food practices adapted to current environmental and social challenges. Giovanni Basciano (AGCI Pesca) and Leonardo Manzari (WestMED Initiative) offered insights into how these practices are being scaled and implemented both locally and across the Mediterranean, reinforcing regional cooperation and policy alignment within the blue

economy framework. UNIPA's involvement in the Italian Blue Growth Cluster (BIG) and WestMED initiatives was also discussed as frameworks for sharing best practices and enhancing regional integration.

➤ Training Session for Small Enterprises

In the afternoon, the workshop hosted a dedicated training session led by Dr. Alessia Careccia from APRE. This session aimed to empower small businesses in the bioeconomy sector by providing practical tools and communication strategies to effectively engage consumers and highlight the value of bio-based products.

The event concluded with a feedback session where participants reflected on the workshop's content, discussing opportunities for replicability and further collaboration. The workshop successfully met its objectives by combining capacity building with knowledge exchange and co-design of scalable blue bioeconomy solutions.

5.1.4 Outcomes

The workshop delivered a set of tangible results that align closely with the expected outcomes defined at the outset of the initiative to **90 participants**. The main achievements are outlined below:

- Knowledge enhancement: participants deepened their understanding of sustainable blue bioeconomy solutions, with a focus on the valorisation of fishery and aquaculture by-products and the development of circular economy business models tailored to coastal regions.
- Model transferability: the Italian pilot case was validated as a scalable and adaptable blueprint, offering concrete strategies that can be replicated across different socio-economic and environmental contexts in Europe.
- Stakeholder engagement: the event facilitated the creation of new connections among research institutions, SMEs, educational bodies, civil society organizations, and local authorities, laying the groundwork for future multi-actor collaborations.
- Positive feedback: participant feedback indicated high satisfaction with the workshop content, particularly in terms of its relevance, practical orientation, and potential for application in real-world settings.
- Community inclusion: the active involvement of local actors reinforced the importance of social innovation and community engagement as key enablers of sustainable transformation within the blue economy.

5.1.5 Findings and recommendations

The workshop offered valuable insights into how community-based strategies can promote sustainable innovation in the blue bioeconomy. Several key messages emerged consistently from thematic discussions and real-world case studies:

- Firstly, social innovation plays a pivotal role in enabling local ownership and co-creation of solutions. Initiatives such as the SMART Living Lab demonstrate how

participatory spaces can foster community engagement and inclusive development.

- Strong links between education and governance can create scalable pathways for sustainable resource use, especially when curricula are co-designed by universities, vocational schools and local businesses.
- Aligning with European initiatives such as Europe Direct Centres and Horizon Europe projects ensures access to broader knowledge bases, partnerships and funding streams, thereby strengthening local efforts through transnational collaboration.

Based on the outcomes of the training activities and stakeholder feedback, the following actionable recommendations are proposed:

Replicate SMART Lab models: Promote and adapt participatory innovation labs in other coastal areas to enable the bottom-up design of blue bioeconomy solutions that respond to local needs.

Develop modular training: Create flexible region-specific training programmes focused on circular economy principles, biotechnology applications and entrepreneurial skills.

Enable multi-actor platforms: Facilitate the development of governance mechanisms that encourage collaboration between public institutions, academia, industry and civil society, fostering shared ownership and value co-creation.

Leverage EU networks and resources: Use EU networks and programmes to access funding, enhance capacity, and foster cross-border cooperation.

5.2 Validation and transfer of new solutions: Estonian HUB

5.2.1 Introduction

The Estonian pilot region demonstration workshops took place in the Saaremaa region on April 2nd 2025, at Abruca conference room; Meri Spa hotel, Pargi Str. 16, Kuressaare, Saaremaa island. It was a hybrid session, with a total of **53 participants were actively engaged during the day** (18 onsite; 35 in Zoom)

The focus of the workshop was to demonstrate the results of the project as well as provide insights from the region by local stakeholders. It featured a dynamic mix of expert talks, practical case insights, and stakeholder discussions, structured to:

- Showcase good practices and innovation examples from the Estonian hub, with a focus on algae valorisation, mussel farming, and offshore aquaculture;
- Share the good practice examples from the Italian, Danish and Greenlandic pilot regions;

- Present hands-on experiences from local entrepreneurs and associations developing blue bio-based value chains in the island of Saaremaa and Ruhnu in the Saaremaa region;
- Share lessons from BlueRev on effective science-business cooperation and communication strategies in the blue bioeconomy sector;
- Stimulate dialogue between researchers, businesses, and policymakers to strengthen Estonia's innovation ecosystem and regional collaboration within the Baltic;
- Promote replicable approaches for sustainable blue bioresource use that align with national and EU-level blue growth and fisheries innovation priorities.

5.2.2 Case study context

The Estonian pilot case study focused on the Saaremaa region, part of Estonia's western archipelago in the Baltic Sea, where coastal communities are increasingly exploring innovative ways to engage with the blue bioeconomy. While traditionally reliant on seasonal fisheries and tourism, the region is now turning toward sustainable marine resource valorisation—particularly the use of algae, mussels, and offshore aquaculture—as a strategic avenue for regional development and diversification.

The Saaremaa demonstration workshop brought together a diverse mix of local stakeholders, entrepreneurs, researchers, and policymakers in a hybrid session that showcased emerging business models based on circular and bio-based innovation. Particular emphasis was placed on the valorisation of red algae (*Furcellaria lumbricalis*), green algae (*Ulva intestinalis*), and mussels, which are being explored for use in cosmetics, food supplements, bioplastics, and ecological packaging. Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture and the combination of macroalgae cultivation with offshore wind energy platforms were also highlighted as promising innovation avenues, contributing both to marine spatial efficiency and nutrient management in the sensitive Baltic Sea ecosystem.

The workshop featured practical case studies from Saaremaa and the island of Ruhnu, where local actors are testing blue bio-based ideas under real-world conditions, despite facing challenges such as limited infrastructure, regulatory barriers, and financing gaps. Local entrepreneurs shared their experience in the R&D of red seaweed and its value chain and macroalgae-based new product ideas. Presentations also addressed cooperative governance models—such as the Estonian Offshore Aquaculture Association—and communication strategies for effectively promoting innovation in the sector.

The Estonian pilot illustrates how even regions with modest marine industries can act as fertile ground for co-creation, experimentation, and capacity-building. The active involvement of public institutions, academia, SMEs, and NGOs reflects a growing commitment to inclusive and collaborative governance. The Saaremaa case serves as a compelling example of how nature-based solutions, blue entrepreneurship, and

community-driven innovation can together foster resilience and unlock sustainable growth potential in the Baltic region.

5.2.3 Activities

The workshop kicked off with Anne Pöder from EMU introducing the project BlueRev. Later on, Mihkel Urmet, a local entrepreneur and representative of NGO Ruhnu Kultuuriruum and Planet Ruhnu, discussed his experience and progress in a macroalgae-based business idea in the presentation “How to sell algae that you don’t have yet? – Vegan fantasies and macroalgae product development news from Ruhnu”. He utilises local maritime heritage and local resources on remote islands, but also struggles with various challenges, including building the required infrastructure and finding technological solutions, finances, and support. He has developed a macroalgae-based gin and is looking into algae cultivation technologies.

Indrek Adler from the enterprise Aqua Verde shared his experience in a presentation, “The pain and gain in setting up a mussel farm”. Indrek has been working on valorisation options for mussels also in these master’s and doctoral studies and provided context on what is the present knowledge, outlook, and promising developments in the Baltic Sea, as well as regulatory hurdles. Mussel farming has the potential to provide a significant contribution in helping to address eutrophication; however, at present, it is not economically viable in the Estonian context and needs further exploration. Mussel farming in trout farms was also one of the new business models discussed in the BlueRev workshops last summer.

A local social innovation and cooperative action case was presented by Georg Linkov from Hiiumere Farm and the Estonian Offshore Aquaculture Association, who shared the story of how they established the producer’s cooperative Estonian Offshore Aquaculture Association and what the challenges have been. The cooperative was established in 2019 and at present has 8 organisations as members. An important aspect of the development has been using the lessons from the failures of previous cooperatives in the field.

Alessia Careccia from APRE provided a training on “How to effectively communicate innovation in the blue bioeconomy sector”, including what to pay attention to in the communication process, what kind of channels to use, how to present innovation in the blue bioeconomy, and how to avoid the pitfalls of greenwashing.

Tanel Ilmjärv from Vetik OÜ is working on red seaweed valorisation and shared his journey that started in 2016. His presentation “Blue bioeconomy in practice: Creation of value chain for red seaweed and science cooperation” discussed the red seaweed as a bioresource availability, the potential use of red seaweed compounds, the economic viability of cultivation, and different products. The enterprise began by exploring pigment extraction technologies and subsequently expanded its scope to include research on biocompound extraction.

Annika Teino from the Estonian Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture provided an overview of the upcoming national research funding measures aimed at the fisheries and aquaculture producers, as well as feedback on what challenges have been challenges from the previous rounds of the funding.

Tarmo Pilving from EMU discussed the coastal tourism opportunities in the blue bioeconomy context in the Estonian islands. The presentation covered practical examples of what format blue bioeconomy-related tourism can take; what services, incl. to production facilities, product tasting, and selling of lifestyle, could be explored; and what would be effective sales channels.

Anne Põder from EMU gave a more detailed presentation on the good practice examples that were collected in the BlueRev project in all three pilot regions of the project. Those include the macroalgae developments and the various social innovation examples the local stakeholders provided in the BlueRev interviews and workshop in Saaremaa. The practices from the Denmark and Greenland pilot regions included fish by-product valuation, an innovative business model for Omega-3 drinks, and a pet food case from Greenland. We used the case of *Ritunnu Salatu* to demonstrate good practices from the Italian region.

The workshop finished with a discussion of the policy recommendation that the BlueRev partners concluded based on the project.

5.2.4 Outcomes

The workshop was followed by **53 participants** and achieved the following objectives:

- Strengthen understanding of circular and sustainable value chains in the blue bioeconomy.
- Build cross-sectoral networks among stakeholders from research, policy, business, and local communities.
- Encourage inclusive approaches by actively involving marginalised and underrepresented actors.
- Collect valuable feedback to guide future actions within the BlueRev project.

5.2.5 Findings and recommendations

The Saaremaa workshop highlighted both the potential and the limitations of advancing the blue bioeconomy in Estonia. Participants emphasised the growing interest in low-trophic aquaculture, macroalgae valorisation, and integrated approaches that combine food production with environmental benefits, such as nutrient removal. However, several barriers were also identified, including lengthy permitting processes, lack of tailored infrastructure, insufficient financing for start-ups, and the limited commercial viability of certain bio-resources under current market conditions.

Key findings from the workshop include:

- There is strong local motivation and entrepreneurial spirit, particularly in remote island communities, to develop innovative marine-based products and services.
- Collaboration between science and business remains essential but requires improved communication, capacity-building, and access to shared research infrastructure.
- Current regulatory frameworks are perceived as complex and not fully adapted to emerging blue bioeconomy activities, particularly for small-scale operators.

Based on these insights, the following recommendations emerged:

- Simplify and harmonise permitting procedures for aquaculture and algae farming to lower entry barriers for SMEs and local innovators.
- Enhance public funding schemes and investment incentives for pilot projects and early-stage companies developing blue bio-based value chains.
- Support the creation of regional cooperation platforms or innovation hubs that connect academia, businesses, and municipalities to foster co-development.
- Develop targeted communication and training programmes to build awareness of blue bioeconomy opportunities, including among youth and coastal residents.
- Explore synergies with offshore renewable energy to advance multi-use of marine space and support circular, climate-resilient solutions in the Baltic Sea region.

5.3 Validation and transfer of new solutions: Danish HUB

5.3.1 Introduction

The Danish Pilot Case Study Demonstration Workshop was held on April 29, 2025 in Aalborg, Denmark.

The focus of this workshop was to validate the results from the BlueRev project with local stakeholders who contributed to the findings with previous work performed during the years, to get their feedback and keep on establishing dialogue and cooperation

5.3.2 Case study context

The Danish pilot case study focused on the valorisation of fish processing side streams and the integration of circular economy practices in the seafood sector. Set in Aalborg, a hub of innovation within Denmark's agri-food and marine industries, the pilot explored advanced technological solutions, including transforming cod by-products into nutraceuticals and implementing automated systems for nutrient recovery from wastewater. These innovations reflect Denmark's broader strategic commitment to sustainable resource management, industrial efficiency, and bio-based transformation.

The BlueRev co-creation activities in Denmark supported iterative prototyping of wastewater treatment and nutrient recovery technologies, ensuring they were not only technically sound but also compatible with the workflows of existing fish processing

operations. This hands-on approach helped local stakeholders gain a deeper understanding of the practical implications of circular transitions in the marine industry. However, the pilot also surfaced challenges—such as high upfront investment costs, infrastructure constraints, and regulatory bottlenecks—which must be addressed to enable broader adoption.

The Danish case exemplifies the effectiveness of integrating technological innovation with social and governance frameworks. By connecting cutting-edge science with real-world industrial needs, the pilot demonstrated how circular practices in the seafood sector can contribute to environmental sustainability while creating new business opportunities in alignment with national and EU-level bioeconomy goals.

5.3.3 Activities

The workshop started with Anni Simonsen from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark introducing the BlueRev project and the topic of this workshop, “Enhancing the Fishing Industry’s Use of Sidestreams”.

Giovanna Ottaviani Aalmo and Maria Bustamente from NIBIO gave the presentation “Presentation and collective exploration of social innovations in the Danish fisheries: How do we address key social challenges through transformative innovations in the blue bioeconomy? They introduced social innovation to the participants, and they also shared the learnings from the BlueRev pilot regions.

The workshop participants were engaged in a discussion regarding the learnings from the pilot regions (Saaremaa (Estonia), Sicily (Italy), Greenland, and of course, Denmark and how participants could use the tools demonstrated to themselves.

Daniel Mattisson from RISE gave the presentation regarding Governance under the headline “How can new governance structures support the development of the blue bioeconomy in the studied pilot regions?”. Results/learnings from the pilot regions were shared in the presentation.

Sougand Golesorkhi from the University of Agder gave the presentation regarding sustainable Business models under the headline “Unlocking Sustainable Business Innovation in the Blue Bioeconomy: Best practices from Denmark, Greenland, Estonia and Italy.

Following the above-mentioned presentations, the participants were engaged in a plenum session, where stakeholders and the speakers discussed the recommendations from BlueRev project as well as opportunities and challenges in regard to enhancing the sidestreams.

Alessia Careccia from APRE presented the guideline for SME’s on how to communicate innovation under the headline “Communication innovation in the bioeconomy sector to customers: the steps for an effective engagement”. It is important for companies to be aware of how and where to communicate with consumers when communicating about sustainability and how to avoid greenwashing.

Rubin Dollerup Nielsen from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark gave a presentation of funding and project opportunities for companies that want to develop new and better innovative solutions for how to use sidestreams.

5.3.4 Outcomes

The workshop saw the total presence of 17 participants onsite, and achieved several key outcomes:

- Provided a platform for stakeholders to explore innovations in fish sidestream valorisation and nutrient recovery technologies.
- Enabled knowledge exchange on social, governance, and business model innovations across all BlueRev pilot regions.
- Stimulated cross-sectoral dialogue on the feasibility and scalability of circular economy strategies within the Danish seafood sector.
- Shared practical guidance on communication and funding strategies to support SMEs developing sustainable blue bio-based solutions.
- Reinforced local stakeholder engagement and encouraged follow-up actions to scale up demonstrated innovations.

5.3.5 Findings and recommendations

The Aalborg workshop confirmed that Denmark possesses a strong foundation for advancing circular economy approaches in the blue bioeconomy, primarily through its industrial capacities, technological know-how, and innovation-driven ecosystem. Participants appreciated the integration of sidestream valorisation with environmental benefits such as improved nutrient management, but also expressed concern over the commercial and regulatory hurdles to mainstreaming these practices.

Key findings include:

- Denmark's fish processing industry offers untapped potential for sidestream valorisation, particularly for producing high-value compounds from by-products.
- Innovation is often constrained by high initial investment costs, lack of tailored funding schemes, and the complexity of navigating regulatory compliance.
- Stronger collaboration between technology developers, processors, and regulatory bodies is needed to accelerate implementation.
- Effective communication with consumers is crucial to build trust and avoid greenwashing when marketing sustainable products.

Based on these insights, the following recommendations emerged:

- Expand public and private funding instruments targeted at pilot-scale and demonstration projects for sidestream valorisation.
- Streamline regulatory pathways to support the uptake of circular solutions within existing seafood industry operations.

- Facilitate the development of industry clusters or innovation hubs focused on circular marine technologies and by-product utilisation.
- Promote training and awareness campaigns to help SMEs improve communication strategies and build transparency around sustainability claims.
- Encourage cross-border collaboration with other Baltic and European regions to share best practices and co-develop replicable models for sustainable seafood innovation.

5.4 Validation and transfer of new solutions: Greenlandic HUB

5.4.1 Introduction

The Denmark/Greenland pilot region held its first demonstration workshop on June 17, 2025, in Nuuk, Greenland.

The focus of this workshop was to present the results from the BlueRev project, gather feedback from stakeholders, and contribute to establishing dialogue and cooperation among stakeholders.

5.4.2 Case study context

In Greenland, the BlueRev pilot activities were centred on identifying circular opportunities in the fisheries sector, particularly through the valorisation of fish sidestreams. Co-creation workshops brought together a range of stakeholders—vessel owners, processing companies, food producers, policymakers, and support organisations—to ideate and develop commercially viable models aligned with global sustainability goals. Key concepts included: production of nutritional supplements (e.g., Omega-3 oils and protein powders), valorisation of cheek meat from cod as a delicacy product, and the establishment of a receiver station near Nuuk's new airport to consolidate and export fresh fish, shellfish, and seaweed. These ideas aimed to reduce waste, create local jobs, and diversify Greenland's blue bioeconomy while addressing infrastructural and regulatory limitations.

5.4.3 Activities

The workshop started with Gorm Vold from Nalik Ventures welcoming all, and Anni Simonsen from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark introducing the BlueRev project and the topic of this workshop, "**Enhancing the Fishing Industry's Use of Sidestreams**".

After setting up the programme with the introduction of BlueRev, the first speaker was Sougand Golesorkhi from the University of Agder, who spoke about business models under the title "**Unlocking Sustainable Business Innovations in Blue Bio-based Industry**", focusing on best practices from Denmark, Greenland, Estonia, and Italy. The Sustainable Business Model Canvas has been discussed and serves as the foundation

for analysis and communication with stakeholders in the regions, as well as in this demonstration workshop.

Suggested Business Models / Projects

Country	Suggested Business Model / Case
Estonia	Algae-Based Business Model Specific case: Nutraceuticals and cosmetic applications of red algae
Greenland	Valorising fish by-products integrating circular practices and waste management Specific case: Dog food from fish processing waste
Denmark	Transforming fish by-products (salmon) into premium Omega-3 health drinks, combining sustainability and health benefits (for export markets). Specific case: Omega-3 Functional Beverage
Italy	Marine By-Product Transformation and Valorisation Specific case: Ritunnu – Sustainable valorisation of by-catch

Figure 2: Presentation on Business models

The aim was to strengthen the understanding of circular and sustainable value chains in the blue bioeconomy and to promote the transferability of pilot models from other pilot regions in European coastal areas to Greenland.

Daniel Mattison from RISE presented “**Governance**” (Figure 3). He started with an introduction to the process used in its work on governance in the regions.

Figure 3: Presentation on governance models

The following initial governance recommendations were described:

1. **ENCOURAGE COLLABORATION BEFORE GOING TO MARKET:** Create spaces where businesses in the same industry can work together on new ideas and solutions before selling them.
2. **EDUCATE POLICY MAKERS ABOUT NEW PRODUCTS:** Help government officials learn about and handle new products made from sidestreams.
3. **IMPROVE COMMUNICATION BETWEEN REGULATORS AND BUSINESSES:** Make sure government agencies and businesses in an industry can work together well to deal with challenges from rules and regulations.
4. **SHOW NEW IDEAS IN ACTION:** Set up demonstrations to show off new ways of doing things and new developments.
5. **REWARD BEING THE FIRST TO TRY SOMETHING NEW:** Encourage businesses to take risks and lead the way in developing new products and ways of doing things.
6. **MAKE REGULATIONS EASIER FOR SMALL BUSINESSES:** Create a guide to help small businesses follow the regulations and understand what might stop them from entering new markets.
7. **SHARE COSTS AND WORK TOGETHER:** Explore ways for businesses and government groups to work together and share costs, making it cheaper to use sidestreams.
8. **ENCOURAGE PEOPLE TO JOIN THE INDUSTRY:** Give people reasons to start and stay in the industry, e.g. gain new skills.

Out of those recommendations, three of them were highlighted for Greenland:

- Demonstrate new ideas in action
- Make rules easier for small businesses
- Share costs and work together across value chains

Social Innovation was covered by Giovanna Ottaviani Aalmo and Maria Bustamante Liria from NIBIO under the title “**Social innovation and relevant successful examples for Greenland**”. The process was introduced (Figure 4). They introduced the concept of social innovation to the participants, and they shared the learnings from the BlueRev pilot regions.

Figure 4: Presentation on social innovation

Giovanna and Maria explained that challenges & lessons learned are:

1. Workforce Gaps: Ongoing effort to attract/train skilled labour
2. Regulatory Complexity: Need for flexible policies to adapt to market and sustainability demands
3. Technical and Social Feasibility:
 - Continuous community engagement is vital for endorsement
 - Replicating success in other regions requires tailored local approaches

They concluded that the most critical social challenges in Greenland are:

- Labor shortage
- Regulatory hurdles
- Financial and technical limitations
- Logistic limitations

Three cases from Sicily were presented to the participants as inspiration for overcoming challenges in creative and workable ways. After that, the workshop participants engaged in a discussion about the lessons learned from the pilot regions and how they could apply the tools demonstrated to their own situations.

Figure 5: Pictures from the workshop

Kristian Ottesen from Royal Greenland presented “**How Royal Greenland works with sidestreams**”.

They define bones, cartilage, shells, heads, entrails, tails, skins, cheeks, blood, milk, and eyes as sidestreams in their productions. Royal Greenland focuses on achieving the most significant possible utilisation of raw materials, resulting in fewer residual materials from sidestreams and creating value-added sidestream innovations that meet the needs

of customers and consumers, while also fulfilling Royal Greenland's responsibility to create a more sustainable value chain.

Participants were informed about how the company works with sidestreams and the various applications it offers. To prepare the other participants for the workshop, where they had the opportunity to discuss how to develop products and businesses based on three selected sidestreams from Royal Greenland.

Highlights from **Greenland's Self-sufficiency Strategy** (Grønlands Selvforsyningsstrategi 2025–2030), which has significant relevance for the use of sidestreams in Greenland, were presented by Anni Simonsen from Food & Bio Cluster Denmark to provide further inspiration before the workshop.

Fish production in Greenland can cover the country's needs almost 4000 times, but still, the government encourages using the extensive resource more optimally, by:

- using larger parts of the fish
- using other species such as mussels, scallops, quabso, sea urchins, seaweed
- utilising bycatch

During the workshop, the two groups (green and blue) generated suggestions for valuing Cod frames, Cod heads, and Cod Intestines.

Participants were invited to contact Mette Jensen (Nalik Venture) for discussions about Greenlandic support options, and Rubin Dollerup Nielsen (FBDG) about international funding and networking with potential international partners.

Alessia Careccia from APRE presented “**How to effectively communicate innovation in the bioeconomy sector when addressing consumers**” a guideline for SMEs on methods for communicating innovation, steps for effective engagement, the need for companies to identify appropriate channels and timing for communication with consumers, and considerations for avoiding greenwashing when discussing sustainability.

- Communication in the bioeconomy sector
- How to write an effective communication plan
- An example from the BlueRev project

5.4.4 Outcomes

The event saw the participation of 14 people onsite and successfully validated the relevance of BlueRev's recommendations in the Greenlandic context and initiated multi-actor dialogue on sidestream innovation, sustainable business models, and governance. Concrete examples from other pilot regions (Italy, Estonia, Denmark) inspired and demonstrated the potential for knowledge transfer and regional adaptation.

5.4.5 Findings and recommendations

The workshop highlighted both the potential and challenges of sidestream valorization in Greenland. Key findings included a strong local interest in developing high-value products from fish waste, but also clear barriers related to logistics, a limited labor force, and complex regulations.

Three governance recommendations emerged as particularly relevant for Greenland:

- **Show new ideas in action** through pilot demonstrations and small-scale testing.
- **Make rules easier for small businesses** by simplifying compliance and market entry pathways.
- **Share costs and work together** across the value chain to reduce individual investment burdens.

Social innovation insights further revealed that fishermen may not always be the most central actors in community innovation. Addressing regulatory complexity, workforce shortages, and the need for flexible, place-based models was deemed essential for successful upscaling. Continued engagement, local ownership, and context-aware transfer of external practices are necessary for sustained impact.

5.5 Final conference

BlueRev launched the idea of organizing a joint final conference with sister projects and other related projects. After checking with several projects related to bioeconomy, the confirmed projects were **BlueBioClusters, BlueRev, Engage4BIO, and SKILLBILL**, three financed in cluster 6 (blue-bio economy and circular economy) and one financed in cluster 5 (renewable energy). The conference was organized in Brussels on the 26th of June and saw the participation of over 85 stakeholders.

It was called “**The Sustainable Futures Conference**” and was conceived as a joint event highlighting innovative approaches to sustainable regional development through the blue and green bioeconomy, skills enhancement, and stakeholder engagement. The event aimed to disseminate tools and results, foster cross-project collaboration, and connect with external stakeholders, aligning local initiatives with European policy ambitions.

The agenda reflected a strategic mix of high-level presentations, project showcases, thematic panels, and interactive world café discussions.

It opened with **Annalisa Corrado** (Member of the European Parliament) outlined the EU’s renewable energy strategy, setting a strong political tone on the urgency of just transition and local empowerment; it was followed by a policy update on the **New**

Bioeconomy Strategy (Speaker TBC) and insights into the **Blue Bioeconomy and Ocean Pact** by **Maris Stulgis** (DG MARE) framed the strategic direction for the sector.

The following section was devoted to a short project presentation, then the pitches set the stage for deeper engagement during the **Project Showcase** that followed, where attendees interacted directly with consortium members and materials. In the BlueRev corner, factsheets and videos on the hubs prepared by LOBA (D5.2)⁹ supported the dissemination of the results of the project, complemented by the presence of Natale Amoroso and its product (Ritunno Salatu); his participation exemplified the tangible market potential and valorization of traditional knowledge fostered through BlueRev, offering a real-life case of local bio-based innovation with replication potential in similar coastal communities.

The afternoon panel “**Stakeholder Engagement**” discussed engagement practices, challenges, and successes; speakers from each project shared concrete examples, particularly from pilot regions, on how stakeholders were involved in shaping solutions.

The following session was an interactive **World Café Discussion**, where participants rotated across four interactive thematic stations:

- **BBC**: Innovation in value chains and ecosystem services;
- **BlueRev**: Business models, governance, and social innovation;
- **Engage4Bio**: Regional bioeconomy integration;
- **SKILLBILL**: Education and skills for a sustainable workforce

This format allowed deeper exchange and cross-project learning, with contributions from a diverse range of actors, including SMEs and regional stakeholders.

The final closing panel, “**Creating Sustainable Futures**” was a high-level reflection that emphasized:

- The importance of **place-based approaches**
- Need for **better governance models and regional cooperation**
- Skills and education as **critical enablers of the green transition**

Speakers included representatives from all four projects, who synthesized learning and identified common pathways forward.

5.5.1 Findings and recommendations

Key messages from EU representatives—such as MEP Annalisa Corrado and DG MARE’s Maris Stulgis—emphasized the importance of regional empowerment, renewable energy, and sustainable value chains within the broader context of EU policy priorities, including the European Green Deal and the Farm-to-Fork Strategy.

⁹ 10.5281/zenodo.15878312

One of the main takeaways from the conference was the critical role Horizon Europe projects can play as **catalysts for structured dialogue**, local value creation, and capacity-building across Europe. Despite their distinct thematic focuses—ranging from blue bioeconomy governance to workforce training for renewable energy—the projects demonstrated that shared challenges such as regional resilience, citizen participation, and skills gaps can be tackled more effectively through **synergistic approaches and co-designed tools**. The cross-sectoral setup of the conference highlighted the power of **multi-project collaboration**, especially when supported by targeted funding mechanisms and policy alignment.

Based on the discussions and shared experiences, a set of **policy recommendations** was formulated, aimed at both EU and national institutions. These include the need to support multi-project and cross-sectoral collaborations, strengthen stakeholder engagement and co-creation frameworks, address territorial skills gaps through tailored training ecosystems, and ensure the long-term sustainability of project-developed tools. Importantly, the conference also called for increased investment in harmonizing educational standards across the EU, integrating artistic and cultural dimensions into the green transition, and building governance capacities at the local level. The event reinforced that the path to a sustainable Europe must be **deeply rooted in local action**, inclusive engagement, and long-term policy vision—anchored by projects that not only innovate, but also empower communities to take ownership of their sustainable futures.

Project leaders concluded by reaffirming their commitment to collaboration and impact beyond the life of the projects, underscoring opportunities for replication and policy dialogue. Drawing from the experiences and outcomes of these initiatives, the following recommendations have been shaped in collaboration and are proposed to support policy development and program design at both the EU and national levels:

1. Promote Synergistic and Multi-Project Approaches

- Encourage funding schemes that connect complementary projects across bioeconomy sectors (blue, green, circular) and renewable energy.
- Facilitate cross-project learning and reuse of tools and strategies to improve efficiency and coherence.
- Strengthen cooperation across fragmented value chains by aligning efforts and creating better visibility of interdependencies.
- Support platforms that enable long-term matchmaking, peer learning, and exchange of tools even after projects conclude.

2. Strengthen Stakeholder Engagement for Co-Creation

- Provide structured platforms and incentives for multi-stakeholder collaboration, ensuring inclusivity and open dialogue.

- Involve SMEs from the outset to enable the creation of viable, long-term business models.
- Include municipalities and regional governments to support continuity through local governance frameworks.
- Support projects that act as idea catalysts—enabling diverse actors (especially those who don't usually interact) to collaborate and shape solutions that are locally grounded and socially acceptable.
- Tailor engagement formats—e.g. satellite meetings, lighthouse experts, or small group formats—to increase participation and facilitate mutual understanding.
- Use clear, inclusive communication to empower citizens, especially marginalized groups, to influence governance and market trends.

3. Address Skills Gaps through Regional Training Ecosystems

- Support the creation of tailored training paths jointly developed by companies, universities, and local actors that reflect territorial needs.
- Invest in Vocational Education and Training (VET) aligned with both market and regional sustainability goals.
- Offer specialized training for public bodies to help decision-makers understand and apply innovative solutions.
- Encourage universities and research centres to co-create training and digital tools that meet practical needs in local innovation ecosystems.
- Recognize the importance of local governance in supporting skilled individuals to stay or return to their regions.
- Address gender gaps in the renewable energy sector by fostering inclusive environments and targeted communication strategies to attract and retain women in STEM and sustainability fields.

4. Ensure Long-Term Sustainability of Project Tools

- Require Horizon Europe projects to integrate a business model for the maintenance and evolution of digital tools and resources.
- Identify potential future tool owners (e.g., SMEs, public bodies, NGOs) early in the project to facilitate post-project ownership and scaling.
- Explore mechanisms to incorporate project-developed tools into EU-level platforms (e.g., Commission repositories) to ensure longevity and accessibility.

- Promote early planning for post-project exploitation and ownership—whether public or private—to avoid tool obsolescence.
- Combine tools with success stories and study visits to enhance uptake and relevance across regions.
- Consider unifying tools across projects and value chains to support broader usability and reduce duplication.

5. Harmonize EU-wide Educational Standards and Procedures

- Streamline cross-border recognition of academic degrees and training certificates to reduce delays in education and mobility.
- Develop common EU frameworks for course content structures to speed up mutual recognition and harmonization.
- Promote the use of AI and digital tools to broaden access to learning, especially for remote students, including: Subsidies for digital equipment; Incentives for developing AI-enhanced educational materials; Dedicated support for online course design and dissemination
- Reduce administrative burdens on diploma recognition and course alignment to enhance academic and professional mobility across Member States.

6. Foster the Role of Art and Culture in the Green Transition

- Recognize and support artistic and cultural interventions as powerful tools to raise awareness, foster inclusion, and inspire creative thinking in the context of sustainability.
- Highlight the value of culture and creativity in shaping place-based solutions and supporting community resilience.

7. Support Local Governance Capacity-Building

- Provide financial and institutional resources to empower local and regional authorities to adopt innovative governance models.
- Align local actions with EU strategies (e.g., European Green Deal, Farm to Fork, Circular Economy Action Plan) by connecting regional actors to policy dialogues and frameworks.
- Enable municipalities to lead continuity efforts after project lifecycles end by providing them with appropriate governance tools and long-term support.

By implementing these recommendations, policymakers can amplify the transformative potential of local sustainability initiatives and ensure their alignment with Europe's broader strategic ambitions for a greener, more inclusive, and competitive future.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable has outlined the final exploitation and replication plan of the BlueRev project, presenting the pathways through which its outcomes can generate long-lasting impacts beyond the project's lifetime. The pilot regions—Italy (Sicily), Denmark, Greenland, and Estonia—have demonstrated how tailored governance frameworks, innovative bio-based business models, and social innovation practices can strengthen the resilience and sustainability of coastal communities.

By combining technological innovation with participatory approaches, BlueRev has shown that sustainable blue bioeconomy models can be co-created with local stakeholders, including SMEs, research institutions, policymakers, and citizens. The integration of governance recommendations ensures that replication strategies are not only technically and economically viable, but also socially inclusive and regionally adaptable.

The exploitation plan provides concrete measures to support entrepreneurs, local authorities, and innovation actors in adopting and scaling BlueRev solutions, while the replication strategy offers a transferable methodology for other European coastal regions. Together, these elements enhance the potential for systemic change, supporting the transition towards a circular and resilient blue economy across Europe.

In conclusion, the results of BlueRev highlight the importance of cross-regional collaboration, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge transfer. The project's legacy lies in its ability to inspire and guide other communities in designing integrated blue bioeconomy solutions that foster economic development, environmental protection, and social cohesion.

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

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